

Defensive Publication — Filing 1 Inventions

Publication Date: 2026-04-22 **Author:** Duncan Ndungu Ndegwa
Affiliation: DevFortress (devfortress.net) **Category:** Computer Security, Credential Protection, Automated Threat Response **Status:** Defensive Publication / Prior Art Establishment. Priority established via Kenya Industrial Property Institute (KIPI) Application No. KE/P/2026/005970

Title

Adaptive Behavioral Security System with Real-Time Closed-Loop Response for Web, Mobile, API, and AI Agent Protection

Summary of Disclosed Inventions

This publication discloses six interrelated security inventions implemented in the DevFortress SDK v4.8.0: (1) Credential Aliasing — replacing real authentication credentials with cryptographically random aliases (supporting 10 generation methods including CSPRNG, HKDF-SHA256, BLAKE3, and FPE/FF3-1) so that a complete breach of the monitoring service yields zero valid credentials; (2) a Three-Mode Closed-Loop Response Engine achieving sub-10ms automated threat remediation via external, internal, and hybrid modes; (3) a Behavioral Baseline Engine using adaptive EWMA across eight feature dimensions for novel attack detection; (4) Cross-Alias Correlation using Locality-Sensitive Hashing for distributed attack identification and simultaneous cluster revocation; (5) Graduated Rate Limiting with alias-scoped, four-stage progressive response including nonlinear latency injection; and (6) a Webhook Nonce Registry for cryptographic replay prevention. All inventions are validated across 7 production applications with 26 attack scenarios and 703/703 assertions passed.

This publication establishes prior art for six interrelated security inventions:

1. Credential Aliasing (Token Alias Security)

A system replacing real authentication credentials (JWTs, session cookies, API keys, AI agent tokens, mobile device tokens) with cryptographically random, non-derivable aliases generated via CSPRNG before transmission to any monitoring service. The system operates across

web applications, native mobile applications (iOS/Android), hybrid mobile applications (React Native/Flutter/Ionic), Progressive Web Applications, and API gateways. The alias-to-credential mapping is stored exclusively within the originating application using AES-256-GCM encryption of forward mappings and SHA-256 hashing of reverse mapping keys. Alias rotation with configurable grace periods prevents race conditions between rotation and in-flight webhook delivery. Fall-back revocation under cache failure uses subjectId-scoped broad revocation to ensure no compromised session remains active. A complete breach of the monitoring service yields zero valid credentials.

2. Three-Mode Closed-Loop Response Engine

An automated threat response system operating in three modes: (a) External — events flow SDK → platform → HMAC-signed webhook → SDK execution → confirmation; (b) Internal — a three-tier in-process engine (deterministic rules, ML scoring, async relay) achieving sub-10ms response without network dependencies; (c) Hybrid — internal evaluation with external enrichment via circuit breaker state machine for automatic failover. A unified audit trail merges decisions from all modes.

3. Behavioral Baseline Engine (A1)

Per-entity behavioral profiling using adaptive EWMA across eight feature dimensions (request rate, endpoint entropy, payload size, session duration, temporal pattern, geographic consistency, error rate, inter-request interval). Deviation scores computed as weighted z-score composites detect novel attacks matching no known signature. A population comparator using Welford's online algorithm addresses cold-start entities lacking individual baselines. Adaptive decay rates ($\alpha=0.3$ learning, $\alpha=0.05$ stable) are selected via coefficient of variation threshold.

4. Cross-Alias Correlation (A2)

Distributed attack detection through behavioral fingerprinting across aliases using Locality-Sensitive Hashing for $O(n \cdot \log(n))$ similarity computation. Online hierarchical clustering with configurable similarity threshold groups behaviorally similar aliases. Campaign signature detection identifies coordinated attacks sharing target endpoints. Cluster TTL, explosion guards, and allowlist mechanisms prevent false positives. Simultaneous cluster revocation terminates all correlated malicious sessions.

5. Graduated Rate Limiting (A3)

Alias-scoped rate limiting (per credential, not per IP) with four-stage graduated response: observation, warning, soft-limit (artificial latency injection with nonlinear function and $\pm 20\%$ jitter making thresholds undiscoverable), and hard-block with escalating cooldowns leading to alias revocation. Per-endpoint hierarchical rate limits and micro-window burst detection.

6. Webhook Nonce Registry (A4)

Replay prevention layered on HMAC-SHA256 signing and timestamp validation. Each webhook carries a 128-bit CSPRNG nonce included in the HMAC computation. A bounded cache (max 100K entries, LRU eviction) rejects duplicate nonces. Format validation and clock skew tolerance (default: 30 seconds) accommodate distributed systems.

Implementation Evidence

All inventions are implemented in the DevFortress SDK v4.8.0 (TypeScript, source-available under BUSL-1.1):

- Credential Aliasing: `credential-isolation.ts`
- Closed-Loop Engine: `internal-closed-loop-engine.ts`, `circuit-breaker.ts`
- Behavioral Baseline: `agent-security.ts`, `cold-start-detector.ts`
- Cross-Alias Correlation: `lsh-cluster-engine.ts`
- Graduated Rate Limiting: `graduated-rate-limiter.ts`
- Webhook Nonce: `webhook-nonce-registry.ts`

Validated across 7 production applications with 26 attack scenarios, 133 events, and 703/703 assertions passed (100%).

This defensive publication establishes prior art. The described inventions are the subject of pending patent applications.